

I Have Ten Vice Presidents

notes from the front line of art-science crossover education

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From the movie Office Space

I work at a university that has ten vice presidents.

Better to say that I work at a university that has ten vice presidents, at present. The number has grown and may continue to do so.

The number does not include deans, vice deans, deanettes, provosts or any other administrators that do not have Vice President in their title. It also does not include assistant vice presidents. I don't know how many of those we have – it's not listed on my university's administrative leadership web page.

The increase in administrative staff, VP's being one example, is not unique to my university. Type "administrative bloat universities" into a search engine and you will find ample articles documenting the rise of administrators at universities and within higher education.

Much has been written on how increased university administration is feeding into rising tuitions; How it is connected to the corporatization of universities, with detrimental effects as public goods and public knowledge become privatized and commercialized. How does me, writing yet more, contribute anything of value? Anything of use?

The reality is me saying more may do absolutely nothing. So why write this essay?
Two things.

Firstly, there is an effect of increased administration and corporatization that has not received as much light as it may deserve. It is one that in-the-trenches workers at universities (e.g., me) know about but it doesn't get said a lot (for reasons that I hope will become clear).

Secondly, I was reminded of an exchange with a colleague about a similar issue:

Me: I can't help but feel we may just be talking to each other to make ourselves feel a little better while the machine plows on (it may even be gaining steam).

Colleague: I agree with your feeling, but it makes any tool that keeps one sane even more valuable.

If enough of us perform useless acts of sanity, to shine or re-shine a light on the downsides of university corporatization, then maybe we can hit critical mass of useless acts that fuse into something of use.

So, what grand insights can I shine a light on that university administrators seem to be missing despite sending out survey after survey to the faculty and working staff asking for feedback on various new initiatives that lead to administrative growth; despite setting up 'listening sessions' with various departments. The first insight is not grand at all. It's simple and it's known well by people who have worked at actual companies or corporations (not universities moving toward corporatization). I am pretty sure it's something administrators at successful companies also know well: A clear sign that a company is in trouble is when those who make the company go, the rank and file, start saying "It's just a job".

"It's just a job" is something that can be heard in the trenches. It's not something any worker will be likely to tell an administrator or put on a survey answer (no matter how anonymous the survey is touted as being). If it becomes felt by enough of the rank-and-file workers who make a company go, then it can reverse the trajectory of a once successful company. My second insight is equally simple: If you turn a university of higher education into a business, into a company, into a corporation then you best be prepared for corporate problems that can take the company down. I don't get a sense that university administrators appreciate that. The rise in the number of VP's and administration in general suggests the opposite as it feeds into problems that stagnate companies, e.g., the feeling that "It's just a job".

"It's just a job" is an issue of motivation and passion. Specifically, a lack of motivation beyond a bare minimum. Vice Presidents like to motivate the rank-and-file workers – it helps justify the job. More VP's leads to more motivation to do more. So that should work to keep the passion in the job or to bring it back if it is waning, right? Wrong. Again, I suspect anyone who has had a job at an actual company knows that's wrong. It's so well known that it's been parodied more than once. My personal favorite comes from the movie *Office Space*. The following is an excerpt from the movie script by Mike Judge:

Peter Gibbons: The thing is, Bob, it's not that I'm lazy, it's that I just don't care.

Bob Porter: Don't... don't care?

Peter Gibbons: It's a problem of motivation, all right? Now if I work my ass off and Initech ships a few extra units, I don't see another dime; so where's the motivation? And here's something else, Bob: I have eight different bosses right now.

Bob Slydell: I beg your pardon?

Peter Gibbons: Eight bosses.

Bob Slydell: Eight?

Peter Gibbons: Eight, Bob. So that means that when I make a mistake, I have eight different people coming by to tell me about it. That's my only real motivation is not to be hassled; that, and the fear of losing my job. But you know, Bob, that will only make someone work just hard enough not to get fired."

An added thing to note, for those who have not seen the movie, is that the Peter Gibbons character would not have told the Bobs (who are administrators) what he told them under normal circumstances. It turns out he was hypnotized to be fully care free at work which led him to be totally honest. His critique of the companies move toward more administrators is seen as a breath of fresh air and gets him promoted into the administrative ranks (oh the irony). Eventually he leaves and finds himself in a job he has a passion for.

Passion is something, that if you told me 10 years ago, could be taken out of university faculty members I would have said your crazy. The passion to teach and to do research if one is in the sciences, create if one is in the arts, engage in scholarship if one is in the humanities is, in my experience, what drove my university colleagues far more than pay scales, portfolios, company cash flow, marketable ideas, branding, public relations, pats on the back from VP's, opportunity to rise up the corporate ladder or any of the other things associated with what one might call 'a corporate job'. There was no way that passion could ever be dimmed. Or so I thought.

Before I continue on the main thread, a qualifier is in order.

I realize that this essay could be dismissed an anecdotal. However, things said in 'company' halls but never documented or passed to the higher ups, are not the type of things that can be examined via academic studies, surveys that lead to graphs, and papers with literature citations. They need to be evaluated via the direct experience of individuals. As well as maintaining my sanity, maybe this essay gets readers to ask themselves if they have had similar experiences.

Back to the main.

When I sensed in myself a corporate *deja vu* (I have worked at an actual corporation), at a place I never considered a corporation (i.e., my university), I started to wonder. Wonder turned to conversation. In conversations with colleagues some variant of the following came up more than a few times: "I feel like it's turned into just a job".

Don't get me or my faculty colleagues wrong here: We know that a job is a big deal and do not mean anything demeaning about the value of work when we say "just a job". The meaning is that the passion has been drained out of it. It doesn't matter what job one has (auto body, insurance company, crowd control – I have worked all three), if the passion for it is drained, then good things will not follow (for the worker or the work).

What's an effective way to drain the passion out of the rank and file? Peter Gibbons can tell you (as can many of my university colleagues): Crank up the number of administrators. Have them send the workers more motivation to do more, from increasing angles and written in ever increasing corporate speak, to help the company reach its full potential (whatever that may be – shroud it in more corporate or branding speak to really drain passion). Increase the administrative chain so it's clear to workers that they no longer have the power to influence agendas in any real way (just too long a chain that takes too much time and effort for information to move through). Increase the number of forms that need to be filled out (especially if you want to do anything 'new'). Make workers compete against each other for company resources (with more forms to fill out, or proposals to write, for the competitions). Put in new software systems, with associated mandatory training, to 'help' the workers navigate the increasing administrative webs that 'support' the corporation.

My corporate speak is rusty but I can end with a corporate speak question to ponder. Corporations like to talk about return on investment (*ROI*). Is the rise of university administrators leading to an increased *ROI*? Administrators draw salaries which increases the *I* in the *ROI*. So, they must also be increasing the *R* in *ROI* or what would be the point (what corporation would be silly enough to create more administrative positions that lead to no positive changes or, at best, to no change at all).

What is the return a university provides to students and parents and to society in general? Not an easy question. Not one I have a simple answer to. I have an opinion as to a key factor (arguably the critical factor). To me, the return universities provide is driven by the passions of the rank-and-file workers at the university – the passions that at one time were, in my experience, the antithesis of “It’s just a job” but that are being drained by rising administration.

In the corporatization of universities, which comes with increased metrics used to evaluate performance, passion is easily mis-valued or mis-read as it does not lend itself to quantitative metrics. Its quality needs to be seen and felt from in the trenches (the very place many administrators left long ago for greener pastures). My observations from in the trenches may be outliers but they make me think that the rise of administrative universities will progressively lower the *ROI* of universities. Can it be turned around? I hope so but I also worry that it has moved well above my company level and the level of the people who actually support the university ... or should I say the corporation.

**“I’m naming you VP of Revolution, Action and Edgy Thinking ...
on one condition ...
that you promise not to change anything.”**

Cartoon from modernanalyst.com

https://www.modernanalyst.com/Resources/BusinessAnalystHumor/tabid/218/ID/3827/VP_of_Innovation.aspx